

Quantitation of camptothecin in *Nothapodytes foetida*

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Camptothecin (1), a naturally occurring compound first isolated from *Camptotheca acuminta*¹, is an alkaloid endowed with significant activity against various human tumours. Camptothecin has also been isolated from *Nothapodytes foetida* Sleumer (Icacinaeae) Syn. *Mapia foetida* Wight. and *Ophiorrhiza mungo* L. (Rubiaceae). *N. foetida* has been reported to contain about 0.01–0.15% of camptothecin (1) accompanied by 9-methoxycamptothecin (2) and other mi-

west Himalaya.

Results and Discussion

N. foetida was introduced for the first time in the north-western agroclimatic region of Jammu and one-year plant was studied for the isolation of camptothecin. The plant was studied into roots, stem and leaves (Table 1). The individual

1. R = H
2. R = OMe

nor alkaloids including polar congeners of 1 (mappicine glucosides and foetidin). Camptothecin belongs to a group of anticancer agent with unique mechanism of action, poisoning of eukaryotic DNA topoisomerase I. Recently, two water-soluble derivatives topotecan (TPT), irinotecan (CPT-II) are showing promising chemotherapeutic efficacy in clinical trials. Simultaneously, 9-aminocamptothecin (9-AC) has been introduced in clinical trials, because it exhibits curative ability against human colon carcinoma and strong antitumour activity against solid tumour xenografts. The currently available source of camptothecinoid is the roots of *N. foetida*. To obtain 1 kg of camptothecin it requires 1000 kg of roots. Several thousand plants must be uprooted to procure this quantity of the root. Compounding this problem is the relative scarcity and the slow growth of the plant. The obvious need for additional sources prompted us to take up this study.

The aim of the present study was to compare the levels of camptothecin in various plant-parts of *N. foetida*. The seeds of *N. foetida* were procured from the Western-Ghats of India and germinated in agroclimatic region of the north-

Table 1. Camptothecin contents in *N. foetida*

Plant part	Fresh wt. g	Moisture content %	Dry wt. g	EtOH-soluble* %	CHCl ₃ -soluble* %
Roots	95	52.60	45	3.0	0.93
Stem	120	59.2	49	11.0	1.00
Leaves	165	75.76	40	2.0	0.20
Seeds**	–	–	100	10.0	1.00

*Percentage based on oven-dried matter. **Seeds : Camptothecin was estimated before germination

Fig. 1. HPLC profile of camptothecinoids from *N. foetida* roots : (1) camptothecin, RT = 6.9 min and (2) 9-methoxycamptothecin, RT = 8.74 min. Conditions : RPC-18 Novapack column; column, 150×3.9 mm; solvent, MeOH-water (60 : 40); flow rate, 1 ml min⁻¹

Fig. 2. HPLC profile of camptothecinoids from *N. foetida* stem.

Fig. 3. HPLC profile of camptothecinoids from *N. foetida* leaves.

Fig. 4. HPLC profile of camptothecinoids from *N. foetida* seeds.

Table 2. Comparative quantitation of camptothecin

Plant part	<i>Camptotheca</i>		RRL Nursery plant
	<i>acuminata</i>	<i>N. foetida</i>	1 year-old plant
	%	%	%
Roots	0.01	0.1	0.106
Root bark	0.02	-	-
Stem bark	0.01	0.08	-
Stem	0.04	0.06	0.073
Leaves	-	0.01	0.08
Fruits	0.03	-	-
Seeds	-	0.1	-

part was extracted with ethanol at room temperature. After filtration and evaporation of solvent to afford a brown syrup, the ethanol extract was partitioned between petroleum ether and water, then CHCl_3 successively. The chloroform extract was concentrated and detected on HPLC. The results (Figs. 1–4) have been compared with the standard camptothecin (Table 2) and it has been observed that leaves can be utilised for the future source of camptothecin as these are renewable mass.

Experimental

N. foetida seeds were grown in the northwestern Himalayan agroclimatic region. The various parts of the one-year old plant, i.e. roots, stem and leaves were collected in the month of November 1996 and dried immediately at 40° .

Finely ground plant material was extracted with EtOH at room temperature. The extract was concentrated, filtered and partitioned between petrol and CHCl_3 successively. The CHCl_3 layer was dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and analysed on HPLC.

HPLC analysis : C-18 Novapack column (15 cm \times 4.9 mm); eluent, 60% aq. MeOH; flow rate, 1 ml min^{-1} ; detection, 256 nm. The contents of camptothecin in various extracts were measured by using standard calibration curves of the authentic sample (Sigma).

References

1. M. E. Wall, M. C. Wani, C. E. Cook, K. H. Palmer, A. T. McPhed and G. A. Wim, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **88**, 3888.
2. B. Xu in "U.S.-China Pharmacology Symposium", eds. J. J. Burns and P. J. Tsuchitani, National Academy of Sciences, Washington, DC, 1980, p.156.
3. M. E. Wall, M. C. Wani, A. W. Nicholas, G. M. Kumar, C. Tele, L. Moore, A. Truesdale, P. Leitner and J. M. Besterman, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1993, **36**, 2689.
4. T. R. Govindachari and N. Viswanathan, *Phytochemistry*, 1972, **11**, 3529.
5. M. Arisawa, S. P. Gunasekera, G. A. Cordell and N. R. Farnsworth, *Planta Med.*, 1981, **43**, 404
6. S. P. Sunasekera, M. M. Badawi, G. A. Cordell, N. R. Farnsworth and M. Chitnis, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1979, **42**, 475.
7. S. C. Puri, G. Handa, T. N. Srivastava and S. N. Sharma, in the press.
8. L. T. Lin, T. Y. Chao and J. S. Hsu, *Hua Hsueh Hsueh Pao*, 1977, **35**, 227 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1978, **89**, 22078).
9. T. R. Govindachari, K. R. Ravindranath and N. Viswanathan, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin. Trans. 1*, 1974, 1215.

